

REPORT

User Requirements of Synthetic Data

Researcher Workshop Results

This report presents the findings from our researcher workshop focused on understanding the user requirements for synthetic data developed from sensitive data within Trusted Research Environments. Through a series of structured discussions with researchers, we explored how synthetic data could support various research activities, identified key use cases, and gathered insights into the characteristics, access needs, and governance models necessary to ensure synthetic data is both useful and responsible. These outcomes will inform the development of practical guidance and future stakeholder engagement to advance the safe and effective use of synthetic data in UK research.

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Table of Contents

Executive Summary	Page 2
Introduction	Page 3
Background	Page 4
What is Synthetic Data?	Page 4
Why is Synthetic Data Beneficial for TREs?	Page 6
Use Cases of Synthetic Data	Page 6
Characteristics of Synthetic Data	Page 7
Results	Page 8
Benefits & Use Cases	Page 8
Concerns & Challenges	Page 9
Increasing Confidence in Synthetic Data	Page 10
Requirements	Page 11
Synthetic Data Levels	Page 13
High-Fidelity Synthetic Data in Research	Page 15
Conclusion	Page 16
Next Steps	Page 17
Acknowledgements	Page 17

Executive Summary

Key Findings

This report presents the findings from our researcher workshop exploring the practical requirements and governance needs of synthetic data developed from sensitive data within Trusted Research Environments (TREs). Discussions focused on six pre-defined use cases to guide requirements of synthetic data: code development, data discovery, researcher training, enhancing analysis, private AI development, and federated analytics.

Code development, data discovery, and training emerged as the most important and immediately impactful use cases for synthetic data. These were consistently identified as areas where synthetic data could deliver major benefits by reducing bottlenecks, enabling earlier and broader access to data resources, and supporting skills development without risking sensitive information.

For these use cases, participants agreed that lower-fidelity synthetic data, which retain structural or basic statistical features without preserving relationships, are generally sufficient. The requirements for these include high data quality, clear documentation, and especially easy accessibility, enabling use outside secure environments. The key advantage of this level of synthetic data lies in its ability to accelerate early-stage work while maintaining a low risk of disclosure.

In contrast, use cases such as enhancing analysis, developing private AI models, and in some cases federated analytics were seen to require higher-fidelity synthetic data that retain more realistic and complex relationships between variables. These applications demand greater analytical utility, larger data sizes, and often preserved correlations to be effective. However, the increased realism also introduces greater disclosure risk, leading to the need for more stringent governance and restricted access.

It was widely agreed that efforts to develop and deploy synthetic data should be prioritised towards the high-impact use cases, particularly code development, data discovery, and training, that directly improve the researcher experience within TREs. These early-stage research activities face the greatest practical barriers due to access restrictions, and synthetic data offers a low-risk, high-value solution to improve efficiency, skill-building, and innovation.

From the results of this workshop, it was clear that there is a need for three tiers of governance models, which will be explored and developed in further workshops:

General Access Governance (for L1 - L2 synthetic data):

Lightweight controls for low-fidelity synthetic data focused on user agreements and documentation/guidance. These datasets should be made easily accessible outside of TREs, especially for exploratory, and preparatory tasks such as code development and data discovery.

Controlled Access Governance (for L3 synthetic data):

This model should enable access to higher-fidelity synthetic data within secure environments (or other appropriate safeguards), with lighter governance than real data. While these datasets carry some disclosure risk due to retained relationships, controlled access allows a greater level of utility while ensuring privacy protections. This approach was seen as especially valuable for researcher training and federated query development.

Restricted Access Governance (for L4 synthetic data):

Equivalent governance to the original datasets. These high-fidelity, augmented datasets are only suitable for use within secure environments due to their strong resemblance to real data and high analytical power.

INTRODUCTION

Researcher Workshop

This report presents the findings from the first workshop hosted by the UK Synthetic Data Community Group, an initiative funded by DARE UK. This group was established to host a series of workshops involving a range of stakeholders including researchers, domain experts, data owners, and members of the public, with the aim of developing governance frameworks, tools, and resources for the responsible use of synthetic data in sensitive data research.

Recognising that synthetic data must ultimately serve the needs of those who will be using it, this initial workshop focused specifically on the perspectives and requirements of researchers and users of Trusted Research Environments (TREs). By establishing user needs at the outset, we aim to ensure that the governance and best practices we develop in further workshops are grounded in practical use cases, requirements and real-world challenges.

This workshop explored the potential benefits of synthetic data, the barriers and limitations researchers may face, and what is needed to make synthetic data a reliable and valuable asset. These insights are critical to guiding the design of governance models and tools in ways that are both usable and impactful. In doing so, we seek to ensure that the resulting frameworks and tools are not only robust and responsible, but also truly fit for purpose.

Participants were recruited through established TRE organisation networks, using mailing lists and social media to reach researchers specifically working with sensitive data, to ensure relevance to the discussions. Among those who attended, 60% reported having some prior experience with synthetic data, 40% had never used it before, and no participants said they regularly use synthetic data. Throughout the workshop, participants took part in group discussions facilitated by the co-chairs, and completed a series of structured questionnaires.

Background

What is Synthetic Data?

Synthetic data often refers to artificially generated data that is designed to replicate certain characteristics of real-world datasets. These characteristics may include structural properties, such as data types, missingness, and value ranges, as well as statistical properties like distribution shapes, summary statistics, and correlations.

Synthetic data exists on a spectrum of fidelity, ranging from low to high. At the lower end, synthetic data may retain only broad structural similarities to the original data, without reflecting the underlying statistical patterns. At the higher end, high-fidelity synthetic data closely mirrors both the structure and statistical behaviour of the source data, making it more useful for analytical or research purposes. As fidelity increases, so too does the potential analytical utility of the data, but this often comes with a corresponding increase in the risk of re-identification or disclosure, highlighting a key trade-off between utility and privacy that must be carefully managed.

Here, it is important to differentiate between two distinct notions of “utility” in synthetic data, analytical utility and functional utility, each relevant to different goals and contexts. Analytical Utility refers to the extent to which synthetic data preserves the statistical properties of the original dataset. This includes accurate replication of distributions, correlations, and other key relationships between variables. High analytical utility is crucial when synthetic data is used for tasks such as statistical modelling, hypothesis testing, or machine learning, where meaningful results depend on the preservation of underlying patterns in the data. Functional Utility, on the other hand, focuses on the actual usefulness of synthetic data for specific tasks which may not necessarily require high statistical fidelity. This includes applications such as writing and testing code, developing analytical pipelines, or supporting data discovery processes. In these cases, synthetic data can serve as a proxy that allows researchers to work efficiently and safely, without the need for a close statistical match to the original dataset. Both forms of utility are valuable, and designing synthetic data with the appropriate type and level of utility in mind is therefore key to maximising its impact while managing privacy risks.

Categorisation of Synthetic Data Fidelity Levels

For the purposes of this workshop, we pre-defined four levels of synthetic data fidelity along this spectrum, providing a framework to support discussion around use cases, utility, and governance needs at each level. These are as follows:

L4: AUGMENTED

At the highest level, synthetic data is generated not to replace real data, but to enhance or extend it. This includes techniques that create synthetic examples for underrepresented cases in a dataset, such as class balancing in machine learning tasks. A common method is SMOTE (Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique), which uses algorithms like K-Nearest Neighbours (KNN) to generate realistic new samples that strengthen model performance.

L3: MULTIVARIATE CORRELATED

This category includes synthetic datasets that preserve relationships between variables, capturing the joint statistical structure of the original data. These datasets are often produced by sampling from multivariate distributions or by using techniques such as generative models (e.g. GANs, VAEs) which aim to replicate the statistical properties and patterns of the original data. The result is a dataset that more closely reflects the real data's complexity, making it suitable for a wider range of applications.

L2: UNIVARIATE STATISTICAL

At this level, synthetic data is often generated by sampling from independent univariate distributions for each variable. This means that each variable's statistical properties, such as its distribution shape, mean, and standard deviation etc, are replicated individually. However, inter-variable relationships (e.g. correlations or dependencies) are not preserved, which limits the usefulness of this data for tasks requiring a realistic joint distribution.

L1: STRUCTURAL

Typically this type of synthetic data is generated solely from metadata, such as data types, value ranges, and missingness. The resulting dataset mimics the structural properties of the original data, maintaining variable types, the range of values, and overall schema, but the values themselves are entirely random. No statistical properties or relationships from the real dataset are retained.

Why is Synthetic Data Useful for TREs?

Trusted Research Environments (TREs) are secure platforms designed to facilitate access to sensitive data for research while ensuring that privacy, confidentiality, and ethical standards are upheld. They typically operate under the Five Safes framework: Safe People, Safe Projects, Safe Data, Safe Settings, and Safe Outputs which collectively ensure that sensitive data is used responsibly and securely.

While TREs play a crucial role in enabling trusted data access, they also present a number of practical barriers for researchers. Gaining access to real data within a TRE can involve lengthy approval processes, often taking months to be able to access. This can delay the start of research projects and create significant inefficiencies, particularly for time-sensitive work. Furthermore, training and education are hindered by these restrictions, as students and early-career researchers often struggle to access real data for learning and skill development. Another limitation is the reliance on metadata to determine dataset suitability. Researchers are often asked to make decisions about whether a dataset will meet their needs without ever seeing the actual data. This can lead to wasted time and resources if, after going through the access process, the dataset proves unsuitable for their intended analyses.

These limitations could be overcome through the integration of synthetic data into TRE services, to accelerate the research process and broaden access to high-quality training resources, ultimately making TREs more effective.

Use Cases of Synthetic Data

Synthetic data can support a wide range of applications, ranging from early-stage research planning to advanced machine learning development. Since many potential use cases have been explored in previous work, we focused on a pre-defined set of six core use cases to support more structured discussions around user needs and requirements. These use cases were chosen for their relevance in addressing challenges around TREs. By narrowing the scope in this way, we aimed to explore how synthetic data could meaningfully complement or enable research in TREs. These six use cases are:

Data Discovery & Research Planning

Synthetic data can play a valuable role in the early stages of research by supporting data discovery and research planning. Before researchers apply for access to sensitive or restricted datasets, synthetic versions can provide a realistic preview of the structure, variables, data types, and the kind of values within the data. This allows researchers to explore what types of data are available, assess whether the dataset aligns with their research needs, and better plan their methodologies. By reducing uncertainty and streamlining the application process, synthetic data can help researchers make more informed decisions about pursuing full data access, ultimately saving time and resources for both applicants and data custodians.

Code Development

In many research settings, gaining access to real-world data can often take months due to ethical approvals, data governance processes, and institutional agreements. During this waiting period, synthetic data can be provided to researchers as a stand-in to develop and test their analytical workflows, code, and data pipelines. Although the synthetic data may not reflect all the nuances of the real dataset, it mirrors the structure, variable types, and general characteristics closely enough to allow meaningful development. This enables researchers to get straight to analysis once access is granted, significantly reducing project delays and improving overall research efficiency.

Training & Teaching

It is often difficult for students to gain access to real-world data for learning purposes. Synthetic data can be an invaluable resource for researcher and student training, allowing learners to practice essential skills such as data cleaning, analysis, and visualisation without the risk of compromising sensitive information. It is also ideal for datathons and workshops, where the goal is to teach or practice

methodologies rather than produce meaningful analysis, ensuring that participants can focus on refining their technical skills.

Enabling Federation & Testing New Capabilities

In federated data environments, such as those using solutions like TRE-FX, researchers are often limited to running queries across multiple data sources without directly accessing the underlying data itself. This can pose challenges, particularly when developing and testing complex queries, as the researcher can only see the results returned by the system, not the data itself. Synthetic data can bridge this gap by allowing researchers to write and test queries on a synthetic version of the dataset first. These queries can then be sent to the real data environments, ensuring that the logic and structure of the queries are sound before running them on the actual data. This process helps streamline query development and troubleshooting, saving time and reducing errors. It can also be used as a means to test technical and governance challenges of setting up federation between different data environments, enabling a way to test new technical solutions while governance is established.

Privacy-Preserving AI Models

AI models trained on real-world data often present significant privacy risks when they are released from secure environments. These risks can include the inadvertent leakage of sensitive information or the ability to reverse-engineer private data. High-utility synthetic data can provide a powerful solution to this issue by offering an alternative that mirrors the structure and statistical properties of real data while providing strong privacy guarantees. Researchers and developers can use differentially private synthetic datasets to train AI models, ensuring that the privacy of individuals is preserved. This approach allows for effective model release from secure environments, while reducing the risk of data exposure.

Enhancing Data Quality and Analysis

Synthetic data can be an effective tool for enhancing both the quality and scope of existing datasets, particularly in situations where real data is imbalanced, incomplete, or insufficient. Researchers can use synthetic data to balance classes in datasets, creating a more fair representation of minority samples. It can also be used to increase sample sizes, improving statistical power and enabling more robust analysis. In cases of missing or incomplete data, synthetic data can be leveraged to impute values, filling gaps while maintaining the integrity of the original dataset. Additionally, synthetic data allows researchers to simulate new scenarios, testing models under conditions that may not yet exist or have not been observed in real-world data.

By categorising these six core use cases, the workshop provided a structured framework to guide discussion around the practical needs, challenges, and priorities of researchers for each of these use cases.

Characteristics of Synthetic Data

To effectively support researchers, synthetic data must be developed and assessed according to a clear set of core characteristics that determine its functional utility and fitness for purpose. These characteristics help establish whether a synthetic dataset is suitable for a given use case, balancing factors such as risk, usability, and analytical potential. Prior to this workshop, we identified and categorised six key characteristics to guide discussions on the minimum requirements for different applications of synthetic data. These characteristics serve as a framework for evaluating the design considerations needed to meet the diverse needs of different use cases. The six characteristics are:

Quality

Data quality in synthetic datasets refers to the overall coherence, consistency, and realism of the data. High-quality synthetic data should reflect plausible values, mirroring real-world logic (e.g. age and employment status should align realistically). High-quality synthetic data should also contain the same sort of errors and inconsistencies found in the real data.

Analytical Utility

Analytical utility measures how well the synthetic data preserves the statistical properties of the original dataset and how well it performs in analysis tasks. This includes distributions, correlations, variance, and other relationships between variables that are critical for data analysis.

Privacy

Synthetic data must minimise the risk of re-identification or disclosure, ensuring that no individual in the original dataset can be directly or indirectly identified. Techniques such as differential privacy, suppression of rare combinations, and limiting fidelity can help safeguard privacy. The challenge lies in balancing privacy with utility, particularly at higher levels of data realism.

Size

The size of synthetic datasets should be appropriate to the intended use, with enough records to allow meaningful analysis or testing. In many cases, synthetic datasets mirror the size of the original data, but this is not always necessary. For training or testing, smaller subsets may suffice, while for tasks such as class balancing or augmentation, larger synthetic samples may be generated.

Accessibility

This includes both technical accessibility (ease of download, level of access controls) and procedural accessibility (low-friction approval processes, integration with TRE workflows). One of the main benefits of synthetic data is its potential to be shared more freely than real data, realising this benefit depends on ensuring that access pathways are clear, equitable, and efficient.

Documentation and Transparency

Good documentation is essential for enabling researchers to understand how a synthetic dataset was created, what it represents, and what its limitations are. This includes metadata, information on the generation method used (e.g. statistical sampling, generative models), known biases, and an explanation of what the data can and cannot be used for. Transparent documentation builds trust and helps users make informed decisions about using synthetic data responsibly.

Results

Primary Benefits & Use Cases

Across the group discussions, there was strong consensus that synthetic data holds significant promise in addressing many of the practical challenges researchers face when working in TREs. A key benefit consistently highlighted was the ability of synthetic data to accelerate research workflows by providing early access to data-like resources before real data becomes available. This was particularly valued in situations where lengthy data access approvals can delay projects for months.

Figure 1: The most beneficial use cases for researchers ranked from most (1) to least (7)

The most widely supported use case was code development and pipeline testing. Researchers emphasised that having access to synthetic data can enable the creation and refinement of data pipelines, statistical scripts, and analysis plans before entering a TRE. This early-stage preparation improves productivity and reduces analysis time once real data access is granted. Many participants had experienced waiting months for data access, therefore cutting down the amount of time it takes to get started on a research project was one of the primary reasons why this was seen as the most beneficial use case for researchers.

Synthetic data was also seen as highly valuable for training and teaching. It was seen as a solution to provide easily accessible data for students and researchers to build familiarity with datasets, practice analytical techniques, and participate in events such as workshops or datathons. In this use case, participants stressed the importance of including imperfections, errors and outliers in the synthetic data so that researchers know how to handle these when it comes to the real data.

Another frequently mentioned application was data discovery and research planning. Synthetic datasets can act as a richer alternative to metadata, helping researchers explore dataset structure, identify relevant variables, and assess feasibility before committing to an access application. Participants said this could improve the quality of research proposals and ensure that researchers apply for the most appropriate datasets. Many participants had requested data which then didn't end up being useful for their research, therefore being able to have a deeper understanding of what is available in the data was seen as a big benefit.

The discussions also noted the important role synthetic data can play in enabling federated research across multiple data environments. In federated models, where data cannot be moved or directly accessed, synthetic data can serve as a powerful enabler for cross-environment collaboration. By providing researchers with synthetic versions of datasets from different TREs or institutions, it becomes possible to develop and test federated analysis pipelines, query logic, and data harmonisation strategies without directly accessing sensitive data. This can act as a proof of concept that demonstrates the feasibility and value of federation before navigating complex governance approvals or building full technical integrations. In this way, synthetic data can help overcome both technical and procedural barriers to federation.

There was less of an interest in using synthetic data for enhancing real-world datasets. Participants recognised the role synthetic data can play in this area such as balancing class distributions in imbalanced datasets, imputing missing data, and even generating new data modalities. These capabilities were seen as particularly relevant for AI model development, where diversity and representativeness of training data are crucial for reducing bias and improving generalisability. However, researchers felt this is something that they would want to implement themselves within their research, instead of having TREs do this for them.

Concerns & Challenges

Despite the clear benefits, several concerns and limitations were consistently raised across the discussions. One of the primary concerns was around utility vs privacy, specifically, how closely synthetic data should mimic real data to be useful, and whether higher-fidelity data increases the risk of privacy breaches. Participants noted that fidelity and risk are not linearly correlated, and the relationship between the two is nuanced. Researchers also expressed uncertainty about how adversary capabilities might evolve over time to be able to reverse-engineer synthetic data to reveal sensitive information.

Another theme was trust and transparency in the data generation process. There was a perception that AI-generated synthetic data can be inherently opaque, making it difficult to understand or audit how it was generated. Without clear documentation or visibility into how the synthetic data was created, it becomes harder to evaluate its reliability and risk. This underscores the need for strong documentation, provenance information, and quality assurance processes, especially with the use of AI methods.

There were also discussions about the limitations in utility for synthetic data. Several participants questioned the practical usefulness of Level 2 univariate synthetic data, which maintains the distributional properties of individual variables but lacks relationships between them. While this type of data may offer a marginal improvement over Level 1, it was seen by some as offering limited additional benefit to researchers. In contrast, Level 1 structural data, though lower fidelity, was seen as more straightforward and useful for basic familiarisation, particularly when it includes realistic patterns of missingness or structural quirks.

Certain data types were seen as more difficult to synthesise, including time-series data, genomics, qualitative data, and highly relational datasets. These types of data present additional complexity in both preserving meaningful structure and ensuring privacy. For example, generating synthetic longitudinal time-series data was described as particularly challenging due to the dense interdependencies across variables and time.

Finally, participants noted the importance of user education and awareness. Researchers must understand that synthetic data is not real data, and therefore should be cautious when interpreting results derived from it.

Increasing Confidence in Synthetic Data

Figure 2: Factors which would increase confidence in synthetic data ranked from most (1) to least (6)

From these concerns, participants were asked what aspects would improve their confidence in using synthetic data. The top priority was the validation of how representative the synthetic data is compared to the real dataset, emphasising the importance of ensuring key characteristics are preserved. From the discussions participants said visualisations comparing the real and synthetic data would help to understand how similar it is to the real data. Additionally, participants felt that synthetic data should cover the whole range of values found within the real data, including inconsistencies and “oddities”.

This was followed closely by the need for detailed documentation of the generation process, which would help users understand the methodology, limitations, and assumptions involved. The importance of documentation was mentioned several times throughout the discussions, and was a central theme to ensuring that synthetic data is transparent and that researchers know how to use it.

Evaluation of quality was also rated highly, reflecting researchers’ desire for some assurance that the data is coherent, plausible, and usable. While privacy guarantees were important, they ranked below representativeness and documentation, suggesting that researchers assume privacy should be a given and are more concerned with whether the data can meaningfully support their work. Analytical utility was ranked lowest out of all factors. From the discussions, researchers valued quality far greater than analytical utility for many use cases.

Figure 3: Minimum requirements for synthetic data, stars mean identified as high importance

Requirements of Synthetic Data

Accessibility

One of the key characteristics discussed during the workshop was accessibility. There was general consensus that lower-fidelity synthetic data (e.g. Level 1 or 2), which may preserve only structural features or limited statistical properties, should be made openly accessible outside TREs, particularly for education, code development, and initial feasibility assessment. Researchers felt that the main value synthetic data brings to researchers is being made easily accessible, without the delays, application processes, and governance barriers often associated with sensitive data. However, researchers recognised that higher-fidelity data (Levels 3 and 4), which more closely resemble real datasets and carry greater disclosure risks, may require tighter security and should typically remain accessible only within secure environments.

For use cases such as code development, data discovery, and training, ease of access was consistently identified as a top priority. However, in the context of training, while lower-fidelity data may often be sufficient, several participants noted that in many cases, Level 3 correlated data would be necessary to meaningfully support training. There was no clear consensus on whether such correlated training data should be available outside TREs. Some researchers saw value in keeping it within a TRE, viewing it as an opportunity to familiarise users with controlled data environments and prepare them for working with real data under similar restrictions. Others argued that this could limit flexibility and create unnecessary hurdles for gaining access.

Documentation

Detailed documentation emerged as a critical requirement across all use cases, with participants consistently stating that they would need comprehensive, transparent documentation in order to trust and use synthetic data. Researchers emphasised that documentation should include clear explanations of how the synthetic data was generated such as, what models, algorithms, or techniques were used, and why those methods were chosen. Researchers particularly highlighted the need to explain methods where AI generative models may be used.

Participants also stressed the importance of understanding the limitations, assumptions, and potential biases introduced during synthesis. Documentation should make explicit any known deviations from the real data, as well as the intended use cases and unsuitable applications for the synthetic dataset. There was particular interest in documentation that provides quantitative metrics and visual comparisons, such as histograms, scatter plots, PCA (Principal Component Analysis) comparisons, or correlation matrices, to help users assess how closely the synthetic data mirrors the structure and variability of the original.

Provenance information was highlighted as another key element. Researchers wanted visibility into what had been done to the original source data prior to synthesis, such as data cleaning, filtering, or anonymisation steps, and how these might influence the synthetic output. Understanding the structure and quirks of the original dataset was seen as essential for interpreting the synthetic data's realism and potential utility.

Quality

Quality was also identified as a critical characteristic for synthetic data across a range of use cases, often regarded as more important than analytical utility. Researchers emphasised that for synthetic data to be genuinely useful, it must accurately reflect the structure and character of the real data, not just in terms of overall similarity, but also in representing the data's inherent quirks, inconsistencies, and imperfections. This included the full range of values, realistic patterns of missingness, outliers, and even errors that are typically present in real-world datasets.

Participants expressed concern that synthetic data which has been overly cleaned or simplified, such as datasets containing only clean, categorical variables with idealised distributions, does not provide a realistic basis for activities like code development, training, or algorithm development. Such data cleaning was seen as removing precisely the aspects of data that make real datasets challenging to work with. For example, when developing algorithms or preparing for analysis, researchers want to encounter the same irregularities, anomalies, and complexities that would be present in the actual research data, as this allows them to stress-test their methods and ensure they are fit for purpose.

There was also emphasis on the importance of consistency within the synthetic data. Participants highlighted that quality also involves ensuring that the synthetic data makes logical sense. For instance, researchers noted that synthetic data should not include unrealistic combinations, such as male individuals being recorded as pregnant, or patterns that violate known rules in the source domain. The presence of such errors undermines trust in the data and limits its usefulness for tasks that require accurate schema and realistic values.

Utility

For higher-fidelity applications, such as enhancing analysis, developing privacy-preserving AI models, and, in some cases, researcher training, high analytical utility was consistently identified as a critical requirement. In these contexts, participants emphasised that without sufficient utility, synthetic data becomes ineffective, as it fails to capture the complexity of the data required for meaningful analysis.

AI models, in particular, were noted to be highly sensitive to subtle and complex data patterns. If these patterns are not faithfully preserved in the synthetic data, models trained on them risk poor generalisability or underperformance when applied to real-world data. Some participants also highlighted the potential of synthetic data to help mitigate bias in training datasets, but stressed that this is only feasible if the data has high enough utility to reflect the diversity and complexity of real populations.

While many training scenarios could be supported by lower-fidelity synthetic data, participants acknowledged that certain types of training, especially those involving analytical techniques or specialised domains, necessitate synthetic datasets that maintain meaningful relationships between variables. For example, learners developing skills in causal inference, time series modelling, or AI model development would benefit from correlated synthetic data that reflects the intricacies of the real data.

Synthetic data was also discussed as a powerful tool for augmenting real datasets to improve analysis. Researchers noted its potential to balance class distributions, reduce bias, and simulate rare events, use

cases that demand augmented synthetic data with high analytical fidelity. The importance of utility was further highlighted in discussions around complex data types such as neuroimaging and genomics. In brain imaging, for instance, participants described how synthetic data can support modality conversion, harmonisation across sites, and enhancement of scan quality. These applications require synthetic data that not only resembles the structure of the original data but also provides meaningful signals that can inform real-world research and clinical decision-making.

Size

For purposes such as code development, data discovery, and researcher training, participants generally agreed that smaller subsets of data are sufficient. In these scenarios, the focus is typically on understanding structures, confirming code runs correctly, or exploring the feasibility of study designs. As a result, full-scale synthetic datasets were not seen as necessary. In contrast, for higher-fidelity use cases, such as enhancing analysis, developing private AI models, or supporting federated research, researchers stressed the need for synthetic datasets to match, or even exceed, the size of the original data.

In federated research specifically, dataset size was seen as a crucial factor. Participants emphasised the importance of using realistically sized synthetic data to evaluate computational load, query complexity, and response times in distributed environments. Testing with small datasets would not expose the performance or scalability challenges that may arise in real-world settings. Therefore, having access to large-scale synthetic datasets was considered necessary to provide an accurate proof of concept for federated systems.

Synthetic Data Levels

From the results and discussions, a clear pattern emerged regarding the minimum levels of synthetic data fidelity required for different use cases. Two broad categories of synthetic data became apparent: lower-fidelity data (Levels 1 and 2) designed for accessibility and high quality, and higher-fidelity data (Level 3 and above) required for more advanced analytical purposes, typically with greater governance and access controls, but with higher analytical utility and size.

Lower-fidelity synthetic data, primarily structural and statistical, was seen as sufficient for data discovery, code development, and many forms of researcher training (it is important to note that these three use cases were identified as the most beneficial to researchers). For these uses, participants emphasised the importance of accessibility and simplicity. Level 1 (structural) data, for example, was valued in code development, where the goal is simply to write and debug scripts. Data discovery required at least Level 2 (univariate statistical), as researchers needed to understand basic distributions and missingness to assess data suitability. In both cases, documentation and data quality were considered more critical than analytical utility, and strong privacy protection was expected to enable access outside of TREs.

Training was identified as a more ambiguous case. While basic training (e.g. exploring methods, familiarisation, or basic code exercises) could be done with Level 1 or 2 data, more advanced training, such as causal inference or complex modelling, was believed to require Level 3 (multivariate correlated) synthetic data. As such, participants viewed training as a grey area, with some arguing for easy access to low-fidelity data, while others emphasised the value of learning within a TRE using more realistic high-fidelity synthetic datasets.

Higher-fidelity synthetic data was clearly required for enhancing analysis and developing privacy-preserving AI. For these use cases, participants agreed that Level 3 (multivariate correlated) or higher was necessary. These tasks depend on preserving subtle relationships and inter-variable structures to ensure meaningful results. In AI development, for instance, the lack of such structure could lead to models that fail to generalise. Similarly, in enhanced analysis, synthetic data may be used to augment datasets or simulate new scenarios, requiring realistic complexity and fidelity.

Federation also emerged as a borderline case. Some participants believed that Level 2 statistical data could suffice for initial feasibility testing. However, others argued that correlated data (Level 3) was needed to properly simulate computational demands, test federated analytics workflows, and uncover practical implementation challenges. Researchers felt that because this would often be only accessible via TREs anyway, then they could access higher fidelity synthetic data for this purpose.

These findings indicate that synthetic data cannot be governed by a single, one-size-fits-all model. Instead, participants consistently expressed the need for distinct governance approaches aligned with the different levels of data fidelity and associated risks.

For lower-fidelity synthetic data, structural (Level 1) and statistical (Level 2) data, participants advocated for a lightweight governance model. These datasets, which do not preserve detailed relationships or individual-level patterns, were seen as inherently low-risk and highly valuable for early-stage research activities like code development, data discovery, and basic training. Researchers emphasised that the key advantage of synthetic data at this level was its potential for open access, unrestricted by the procedural and technical barriers of secure environments. This accessibility enables broader engagement, supports learning and innovation, and reduces the resource burden on researchers and data owners alike. Accordingly, governance for these data types should focus on transparency, documentation, and responsible use guidelines, rather than access restrictions.

In contrast, higher-fidelity synthetic data, correlated (Level 3) and augmented (Level 4) data, was recognised as necessitating a more robust and risk-aware governance framework. Because these datasets more closely replicate the structure, variability, and potential sensitivity of real-world data, participants widely agreed that stricter access controls, user agreements, and safeguards would be necessary. Use within TREs or under controlled conditions was generally seen as the appropriate model for managing these higher-risk synthetic datasets. However, participants also made a clear distinction between the governance needs of Level 3 and Level 4 data. While Level 4 synthetic data was considered comparable in sensitivity and disclosure risk to the source data itself and therefore should be governed to the same standards, Level 3 data was seen as warranting a more balanced approach. For Level 3, participants felt that while some restrictions are necessary, access and governance should still be lighter than for real data, to preserve the value of synthetic data in enabling earlier and easier access to data.

Figure 4: Governance models for synthetic data

From this, the need for three different governance models emerged. First, an open access model for low-fidelity synthetic data (Levels 1 and 2), designed to maximise usability and accessibility for tasks that carry minimal privacy risk. This model would prioritise transparency, documentation, and clearly stated usage limitations, rather than enforce strict access controls. Second, a moderate governance model for correlated data (Level 3), where a balance must be struck between enabling utility and managing risk. In this case, access should be within a TRE with user agreements or conditions of use, but with lower application and access barriers. In some cases, this synthetic data could be made available outside of a TRE, but only with appropriate safeguards and privacy guarantees in place. Finally, a high governance model for augmented synthetic data (Level 4), which, due to its potential to closely mimic or embed real data, should be treated with the same data protection standards as the original datasets, including restricted access within TREs and full auditability. These models reflect both the diversity of use cases and the varying levels of risk and realism that different types of synthetic data present.

The Use of High-Fidelity Synthetic Data in Research

Participants additionally engaged in discussions around the potential for high-fidelity synthetic data, correlated and augmented datasets (Levels 3 and 4), to be used directly in research. Overall, participants were cautiously optimistic but emphasised that clear conditions must be met before synthetic data could be fully trusted as a basis for analysis, publication, or policy-relevant findings.

Figure 5: Concerns with using high-fidelity synthetic data in research ranked from highest (1) to lowest (6)

There was broad agreement that high-fidelity synthetic data is best suited for methodology-focused research, such as algorithm development, model prototyping, or proof-of-concept studies. In these contexts, participants felt that synthetic data could be a powerful enabler, particularly when real data is sensitive, difficult to access, or limited in scope. Use cases involving non-tabular data, such as neuroimaging, ECG, or genomic data etc., were seen as especially promising, though participants acknowledged that these data types introduce additional challenges for privacy assessment and utility validation.

Many participants felt uncomfortable with the idea of publishing findings based solely on synthetic data unless those findings were validated against real data. Trust in results was closely tied to the availability of validation mechanisms. The synthetic dataset's fidelity to the real data, especially with respect to correlations, subgroup patterns, and rare events, was seen as critical. Without validation, researchers expressed concerns that analyses could produce misleading results or amplify existing biases, particularly when studying minority populations or rare conditions. At the same time, there was acknowledgement that synthetic data could be used to help mitigate representational bias in real data, if generated appropriately.

Participants stressed the need for detailed transparency about how the data was generated, the model architectures and training data used, any limitations or known weaknesses, and how the synthetic data compares to its real counterpart. Without this documentation, researchers said they would not trust or use synthetic data for research purposes, particularly in fields requiring high levels of scrutiny such as clinical, epidemiological, or policy-driven work.

Some participants compared the use of synthetic data in research to simulation practices in the scientific community, noting that simulation has long played a role in hypothesis testing and methodological development. However, others expressed concern about peer review acceptance, reproducibility, and ethical considerations, especially in the absence of widespread researcher training and standardised frameworks.

Despite these concerns, many participants recognised the potential of high-fidelity synthetic data to expand access to previously inaccessible data domains, allow early-stage testing of methods, and reduce dependence on highly controlled real datasets. While there is still hesitation around using synthetic data as the sole basis for scientific conclusions, there was clear consensus that, with strong documentation, validation pathways, and transparency, high-fidelity synthetic data can play an important and complementary role in the research ecosystem.

Conclusion

This workshop provided a rich and multifaceted view of the current landscape of synthetic data use in research and the diverse requirements of its users. Across a range of use cases, from data discovery and researcher training to advanced analytics and federated research, participants consistently expressed both optimism about the potential of synthetic data and caution about the challenges involved in its implementation.

One of the clearest takeaways was that synthetic data is not a one-size-fits-all solution. Instead, its value and associated risks are highly dependent on the level of fidelity and the specific task at hand. For early-stage research activities such as feasibility assessments, code development, and exploratory data discovery, lower-fidelity synthetic data (Levels 1 and 2) was seen as not only sufficient but highly desirable. Although these only required lower levels of fidelity, they were seen as having the greatest potential impact. Participants stressed that for these tasks, synthetic data should be made openly accessible, with minimal access barriers, so that researchers, especially those new to secure data environments, can gain early insight into data structures, variable types, and potential suitability for research questions. Importantly, however, low-fidelity synthetic data must be of high quality, realistically reflecting the structure, quirks, and messiness of real data to be truly useful.

In contrast, for more complex and sensitive use cases such as enhancing analysis, developing privacy-preserving AI, or running federated queries, participants emphasised the need for higher-fidelity synthetic data (Levels 3 and 4). These use cases demand not only greater analytical utility, but also large volumes of data and robust preservation of statistical and structural relationships. As such, the risks of re-identification or misuse increase, and so do the expectations for stronger governance, access controls, and transparency around data generation methods.

The discussions also highlighted the importance of comprehensive and interpretable documentation as a non-negotiable requirement for all levels of synthetic data. Participants made clear that without clear guidance on how the data was generated, what it can and cannot be used for, and how it compares to real data in terms of structure, distribution, and bias, they would be cautious to use it. Provenance information, visual validation techniques, and standardised metrics were all seen as key components of usable documentation.

The workshop revealed that two distinct governance models are required for synthetic data to

be useful and trusted at scale. One model should support easy access to low-fidelity synthetic data for data discovery, training, and early-stage research, supported by strong privacy protections and quality standards but minimal procedural barriers. The other should govern access to high-fidelity synthetic data with enhanced safeguards, formal access agreements, and oversight mechanisms appropriate to its greater resemblance to real data.

The workshop reinforced the potential of synthetic data as an enabling tool across the data lifecycle, bridging access gaps, supporting ethical data use, and reducing reliance on sensitive data when it is not strictly necessary. In summary, synthetic data is not a singular solution but a flexible spectrum of tools and methods. Realising its full potential will require investment not just in technical generation methods, but in user-focused documentation, governance frameworks, and education resources. As interest and use of synthetic data continue to grow, grounding its development in the practical needs and concerns of researchers will be key to ensuring it delivers value, safeguards privacy, and supports responsible innovation.

Next Steps

Building on the insights gathered from this researcher workshop, the next phase of this project will focus on turning these findings into practical guidance and implementation strategies. To do this, we will host a series of workshops with expert stakeholders and data custodians.

In a dedicated expert workshop, we will bring together synthetic data developers and methodological experts to explore the technical requirements for generating and evaluating synthetic data that meets the specific needs of each use case. This will include discussions on fidelity levels, validation methods, documentation standards, and assessment of utility, privacy and quality.

We will also host a separate data custodian workshop which will explore how synthetic data can be integrated into data access workflows within TREs, and what governance frameworks, risk assessments, and operational processes are needed to support safe and effective use.

Together, these workshops will help develop a practical roadmap for enabling the generation, evaluation, and governance of synthetic data that improves the research experience while maintaining privacy, trust, and utility. These efforts will be key to unlocking the full potential of synthetic data within TREs and ensuring it is used responsibly and meaningfully across the research community.

Acknowledgements

We would like to extend our sincere thanks to all the participants of the researcher workshop for their valuable time, insights, and thoughtful contributions. Their opinions and open discussions played a crucial role in shaping the findings of this report.

We are especially grateful to the community group co-chairs for their leadership in facilitating engaging discussions and helping to develop the structure and content of the workshop sessions. Their guidance was instrumental in ensuring the conversations remained focused, inclusive, and productive.

We also wish to thank the administrative support team for their behind-the-scenes efforts in organising and setting up the workshop.

Finally, we gratefully acknowledge DARE UK (Data and Analytics Research Environments UK) for funding this work and supporting efforts to improve the safe and effective use of synthetic data in trusted research environments.

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